

ANGLE OF INCIDENCE STUDY AT PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES WITH POLYMER FRONT SHEET

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ABSTRACT:

For years, photovoltaic systems have been successfully installed on a large scale on open spaces as well as at buildings (BAPV) and on buildings (BIPV). For the applications, PV modules in the classic glass-backsheet or glass-glass design are mostly used because their properties are well known. For BIPV and further on for automotive applications (VIPV) it makes sense to reduce the weight of the modules in order not to overload the building's loadbearing capacity statics as well as for vehicles to minimize their energy consumption. One approach for weight reduction is by replacing glass with polymer materials. The light coupling on typical PV modules is largely optimized by means of an anti-reflective coating (ARC) on the front glass. This has not yet been done for polymer front sheets, but this paper will take the first step and characterize different lightweight approaches based on polymer front sheets with different solar cell types (SHJ, IBC) for their skewing behaviour and then give an evaluation of the electrical yield for angle-dependent installation as well as for different locations.

Keywords: light weight, energy yield, angle of incidence

1 INTRODUCTION

A typical PV-module has glass as front sheet. In order to decrease the optical losses and increase energy yield the glass is anti-reflective coated (ARC). Optimised parameters of those layers are a thickness of $d = 120\text{nm}$ and a refractive index $n = 1.23$ [1]. Another approach to couple more sun rays into the module is to increase the glass area by structuring the glass on the air/glass interface. To model the AOI effect an empirical model has been developed Martin *et al.* [2]. In 2006 Grunow *et al.* showed data for outdoor AOI measurements [3].

Within this study we will show the optical properties of polymer front layers as well as the optical differences between samples with glass and polymer front sheets.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Test Samples

For our investigations we designed and laminated four different samples with polymer front sheets and different refractive index. The designs and sample properties are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Module Design

Sample number	A Front sheet: polycarbonate	B Front sheet: Polycarbonate
Design		
Shape	Flat	Flat
Sample number	C The design is presented in [4]	D (1/2 cell)
Design		
Shape	Flat	Flat

At the test cell in the centre of the sample the IV-Curves were measured. The surrounding cells are dummy ones. Those cells will simulate the internal reflection as it exists in full size modules.

The determination of the optical losses will be done by comparing the results of the polymer front sheet samples with identical samples with ARC glass (thickness 3.2 mm) as front sheet.

2.2 Testing

In a first step the spectral transmission of the polymer front sheets and encapsulation materials was measured. The data were recorded with a Lambda 1050 UV/VIS/NIR spectrophotometer device. The measurement interval of the wavelength was $d\lambda = 1$ nm. Additional to the spectrometer analysis the surfaces were investigated with a profilometer to receive information on the roughness of the outside of the polymer front sheets.

We also determined the angle of incidence (AOI) behaviour of all samples with polymer front sheet as well as of the reference samples with ARC glass as frontend. The IV Curves were measured in 10° steps and at $>60^\circ$ every 5° . In order to eliminate the light reflection inside the flasher – a second measurement with a mask located 40 cm in front of the module was done.

Figure 1: Sample A mounted in the AOI set-up.

The following equation has been applied to evaluate the AOI measurements.

$$rel I_{sc} = \frac{I_{sc,total} - I_{sc,diff}}{\cos(\alpha)} \quad (1)$$

The next chapter presents the results.

3 RESULTS

The following figures display the results of the spectral transmission of the encapsulation materials and polymer front sheets.

Figure 2: Spectral transmission of the different front sheets.

Nearly all samples show similar transmission except sample D. That sample is additional UV open, while others block it. In the range of 400...1150 nm the transmission of all samples is with around 90% slightly lower than glass.

Figure 3: Spectral transmission of the different encapsulation materials.

Samples C & D are UV open compared to the other samples. The transmission rate of around 90% in the range of 400...1150 nm is quite similar. At wavelengths > 1150 nm a reduction in transmission is visible. It is assumed that the reduction acts like a heat shield for the cell.

The roughness of the samples was investigated since (micro)structures on the outside of the front glass can lead to a higher performance at higher incidence angle. The results of the profilometer analysis are shown next.

Figure 4: Roughness of sample A.

The figure makes clear that sample A has a smooth surface. The peak at length 3,750 μm seems to be an aberration.

Figure 5: Roughness of sample B.

Sample B's surface is rougher than the one from sample A. However, the surface sample C rougher.

Figure 6: Roughness of sample C.

Figure 7: Roughness of sample D.

The surface of sample D has some peaks, but it seems smoother compared to sample C. The roughness results were evaluated based on the R_a arithmetic centerline roughness value what is defined as:

$$R_a = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l |z(x)| dx \quad (2)$$

and the R_q square center roughness value

$$R_q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{l} \int_0^l z^2(x) dx} \quad (3)$$

Next to them also the Peak and Valley were considered for the analysis of the data. Table 2 presents the average results of four roughness measurements per sample.

Table 2: Evaluation of the surface investigations

	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D
R_a / nm	35.6	822.7	2066.8	785.6
R_q / nm	67.2	1051.4	2988.0	1022.0
Peak / nm	755.2	1544.8	13292.8	3964.6
Valley / nm	-115.6	-4236.4	-6994.9	-2648.2

Table 2 displays the different surface properties. Summarised sample A has the flattest surface while sample C is mostly structured. It can be assumed that the structure is a copy of the membrane from the laminator. If the power output benefits from the structure at high incidence angle will be shown next.

Figure 7: AOI results from all the samples with polymer front sheet and ARC glass as well as with glass without ARC for sample A.

All shapes following the Fresnel equation ($\frac{I_{sc} - I_{diff}}{2}$). For all samples it is visible that for angles $<40^\circ$ there is no major difference in the AOI between glass and polymer front sheet samples. At angles $>40^\circ$ the glass samples show a higher current.

Figure 8: Relative deviation from polymer front sheet sample to reference sample ARC glass.

In this plot, the angle-dependent optical losses of the polymer front sheet samples are compared to the identical references with ARC glass. Sample C shows the largest deviation over all angles. In a final step we simulated the energy yield with the different AOI measured data.

Figure 9: Energy losses related to optical losses due to different front sheets.

At both sites, optical losses are lowest at 30° south orientation (Berlin: < -4.6%; Seville: < -3.0%). In Germany the max optical losses for a polymer front sheet sample is -7.0% and for Spain -7.6%.

Figure 10: Energy yield losses due to different front sheets relative to ARC glass.

The simulated energy yield considering the different optical properties leads to a reduction of $\leq -2.8\%$ (worst case: Horizontal installation) for Berlin / Germany. For Seville / Spain we simulated a worst-case reduction of -2.7% (vertical south installation). However, the losses depend strongly on the installation orientation. The simulations were done with PVsyst for period of one year.

4 SUMMARY

In our investigations we designed and laminated four different samples with polymer front sheets and identical samples with ARC-glass. We did analysis of the optical properties from the polymer front sheets and encapsulation materials like spectral transmission and did investigations of the surface roughness from the polymer front sheet. We determined the angle of incidence (AOI) on the samples, determined the angle-dependent optical losses compared to the ones with ARC-Glass and finally we simulated the energy yield losses due to the different front sheets. We can summarize:

- All polymer front sheets show a transmission of $\sim 90\%$ at $\lambda > 400\text{nm}$. Sample D's front sheet is UV open, while the other samples UV light blocking.
- The polymer frontsheet samples have a different roughness. The range covers from nearly flat (Sample A) to $12\mu\text{m}$ (Sample C).
- The ARC-Glass references show a better AOI compared to the polymer frontsheet samples. Also, the glass without ARC of sample A is slightly better than the ones with polymer frontend.
- Sample C shows the largest and sample D has the smallest deviation over all angles compared to the ARC-Glass.
- No clear correlation between the surface roughness and the optical losses could be seen.
- In Germany the max optical losses for a polymer frontsheet sample is -7.0% and for Spain -7.6%.
- The relative energy yield losses due to different optical properties compared to samples with ARC glass are $\leq -2.0\%$ for Berlin/Germany and $< -2.7\%$ for Seville/Spain.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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